

APPRAISING THE EFFECTIVE PRECIPITATION, EVAPOTRANSPIRATION, AND IRRIGATION WATER REQUIREMENTS OF GINGER (ZINGIBER OFFICINALE) CULTIVATION FOR PRODUCTION OPTIMIZATION

Okolotu G.I.

Department of Agricultural Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Southern Delta University, P.M.B. 05., Ozoro, Delta State of Nigeria, West Africa

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18609229>

Keywords

*Effective precipitation;
Evapotranspiration;
Evaporation;
Transpiration;
Irrigation Water Requirement;
Ginger; etc.*

Abstract: *Precipitation is a major augmentation in field irrigation. However, not all precipitates supplied to fields are effectively used. Some definitely are lost in one way or another, like evapotranspiration. Also, every crop has a certain dose of water it requires for proper functions. Overdose or underdose poses negative effects. This work appraisingly studied the effective precipitation, evapotranspiration, as well as the water requirements of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) cultivation in irrigation systems for production optimization. Upon precipitate capturing and recordings through appropriate meteorological means, the amount of precipitation duly utilized by plants in the field, otherwise known as effective precipitation, was obtained. On the other hand, the evaporation and transpiration capturing and recordings were used in obtaining the evapotranspiration. These were accompanied by comprehension of the specific water required for plants (ginger) for optimum growth in irrigation systems. Resultantly, the effective precipitation was 34595 mm on a daily basis with 629 mm on average, and the total monthly value was 35493 mm with an average of 3549 mm. Evapotranspiration was 427 mm on a total daily basis, with an average of 8 mm, as well as a monthly total of 2417 mm, averaged at 242 mm. The irrigation water requirement recorded a total of -31906 mm with an average of -580 mm on daily basis, and a total of -33076 mm, averaged at -3308 mm on a monthly basis. The resultants sets pace for agricultural decision-making of verse kind. These data will help in monitoring and keeping records useful in managing observable changes (climate, soil reservoir, and others) in the area with respect to farmlands.*

Okolotu G.I.

I. INTRODUCTION

Optimizing production is a major goal in agriculture. This include application of innovations in maintaining good cultivational environment for agriculture to thrive. Irrigation precision provide avenues of such, through developed techniques validatively tested. Prior this research enquiry, previous studies on effective precipitation, evapotranspiration, and irrigation water requirements of plants abound. In case of ginger plants, none laid emphasis on the above stated. This work therefore fills the research gap of providing the data with respect to the ginger plant and the above stated, specifically in the study area. Also, global demand for more production of food increases on daily bases (Okolotu *et al.*, 2025), calling on strategic advancements. Advances in the knowledge of effective precipitation, evapotranspiration, and irrigation water requirements will contribute positively to an optimum agricultural production.

Effective precipitation refer to the amount of precipitation effectively utilized in the field by irrigated crops. Precipitation is any liquid or frozen water that forms in the atmosphere and falls to earth (NGS, 2023). Precipitation is the main way atmospheric water returns to the surface of the arth (WSC - USGS, 2019b). Precipitation is a fundamental component of the global water cycle and a key hydrologic variable of the water cycle for meteorology, climatology, and hydrology (Liang and Wang, 2020). Precipitation is the driving force behind all hydrologic processes, and without it, there can

be no infiltration, transpiration, surface runoff, baseflow, channel flow, or any other hydrologic process (USACE - HEC, 2024). Precipitation is water released from clouds in the form of freezing rain, rain, sleet, snow, or hail (WSC - USGS, 2019b). When and where precipitation falls is determined by the climate system especially by the patterns of atmospheric and ocean circulation, and how much water returns in the atmosphere (UCMP, 2025). Accordingly, effective precipitation is defined as the total amount of precipitation that contributes to the evapotranspiration requirements of a crop cover by reducing a particular amount of irrigation water needed (Muratoglu *et al.*, 2023). Effective precipitation refer to the quantity of precipitation that enters the soil upon application, and becomes usefully available to the crops. During drier periods less than 5mm of daily rainfall would not be considered effective, as this amount of precipitation would likely evaporate from the surface before soaking into the ground. But in an instant where a moisturized soil with less irrigation water requirement receive same quantity in the root zone, the same quantity of precipitation may be considered effective. This is because the 5 mm precipitation will be available to the reach of the crop root for its functions. Muratoglu *et al.*, (2023), pointed that the parameters that affect effective precipitation are grouped into three classes: precipitation (amount, frequency, times of occurrence, intensity, *etc*), land/soil information (topography, surface depth to the groundwater, infiltration rate, water holding

Okolotu G.I.

capacity, evaporation, *etc*), and crop characteristics (cultivation periods, evapotranspiration, crop coefficients, *etc*).

Evapotranspiration is a water exhalation processes involving evaporation and transpiration. Evaporation accounts for 90 % of the earth's atmospheric moisture, the other 10 percent is due to plant transpiration and a very small amount from sublimation (DETSIQ, 2023). In the hydrologic cycle, evapotranspiration is the sum of the two processes of evaporation and transpiration, which are responsible for returning water to the atmosphere, from the surface of objects containing liquid water, such as lakes and streams, soil, and organisms (Sundberg, 2023). It is a critical process within the hydrologic cycle – the transformation of water from the liquid to vapor phase cools down the surrounding atmosphere, contributes to cloud formation, and acts as a distillation process creating pure H₂O, while transpiration is a key mechanism that moves water and nutrients through plants (CUSWL, 2024). Evaporation is the process that changes liquid water to gaseous water (water vapor), occurable when energy (heat) forces the bonds that hold water molecules together to break (WSC - USGS, 2019a). During the evaporation period, the water exist in gaseous phase of matter, allowing the convertible water molecules to mingle with air and other components of the atmosphere. Once evaporated, a water molecule spends about 10 days in the air (WSC - USGS, 2019a), before converting to any of the other two (liquid or

solid) of the three phases of water. Transpiration involves the loss of water vapor from plants, primarily through pores called stomata (Sundberg, 2023). This also helps in nutrient transport from the root zone to plants leaves. According to CSU - CCCC (2025), more than 99.9% of the water used by an irrigated crop is drawn through the roots and transpires through the leaves with small amount (0.1%) of the water taken up by plants being used to produce plant tissue. The concept of developing an open-access ET databases for ET-based agriculture water management is under development by various organizations such as the US Geological Survey, US Department of Agriculture, the Commonwealth Science and Industrial Research Organization of Australia, and the Chinese Academy of Sciences (Wanniarachchi, and Sarukkalige, 2022). Solar radiation or sunlight, air temperature, wind speed, and, relative humidity are the main weather factors that influence evapotranspiration. Generally, as sunlight, temperature, and wind increase and as relative humidity decreases, ET of a plant or planted area increases, provided soil water content is adequate (UCANR, 2025). This is to say that the evapotranspiration rate will drop if the water quantity in the soil diminish, even if the weather factors support a high rate condition for evapotranspiration. Irrigation also increasingly influence evapotranspiration by adding more water which increases the wetness of the soil, and consequently increasing the water amount that evaporates from soil surfaces as well as

Okolotu G.I.

transpiration from plant surfaces. Evapotranspiration is measured and reported on daily record which can be translated to monthly and yearly bases. UCANR, (2025), recommendably emphasized that, a single standardized value known as ETo or reference ET can be calculated at numerous locations to

reflect the influence of local weather and climate on plant water use, to reduce the cumbersomeness and complexity in generating ET values each day in numerous locations for thousands of different plants. ET and other water movement variables of the hydrological cycle are presented in figure one (1) below;

Figure 1: Evaporation, transpiration and precipitation water movement processes of the hydrological cycle (NOAA, 2023)

Irrigation water requirement refers to the irrigation water need of plants. A lack or excess of water causes problems. Precise water requirement is very important for accurate management and conservation of agricultural water (Wanniarachchi, and Sarukkalgige, 2022). Insufficient water, cause water stress, which eventually affect productivity. Also, excess water lead to root suffocation, diseases, nutritional disorders, *etc.* Despite 95% of agricultural land being primarily rainfed, increasing water scarcity can have a negative impact on cropland productivity (Fitton *et al.*, 2019). Water

requirements is vital for efficient and optimum use of water. To accomplish the efficient use of water, experts rely on data collected by soil, plant, and atmosphere to manage properly the irrigation requirements of the crops (Mylonas *et al.*, 2020). To maximise crop yields, it would require a 146% increase in global irrigation water use (Fitton *et al.*, 2019).

Ginger is a worldwid useful plant cultivated by burying the root halfway beneath the soil. It is commonly known as ginger, belonging to the family of Zingiberaceae, botanically named *Zingiber officinale*, and named "zangabil" in Persian (Khodaie and Sadeghpour, 2015). Historical evidence indicates that ginger was originally indigenous to Southeast Asia (today's

Okolotu G.I.

northeast India), cultivated for thousands of years as a spice, and during medieval times, it was exported from India to other parts of the world (Jakribettu *et al.*, 2016). At present, India remain a ginger import nation to Nigeria. Zingiberis” is the Greek word derived from the Sanskrit “shringavera” meaning “shaped like a deer's antler's” (Vasconcelos *et al.*, 2019). Edible ginger is the knobby, fat, aromatic rhizome of Zingiber officinale, a tender herbaceous perennial plant, native to humid, partly - shaded habitats in moist tropical and subtropical forests of Southeast Asia (WHDE, 2025). Some medicinal application of ginger include: a tonic for the memory and digestive system, the hepatic obstructions opener, aphrodisiac, for expelling compact wind from stomach and intestine, diluting, desiccating and emollient of phlegmatic and compact humor sticking to stomach, intestine, brain and throat, a vermifuge and remedy for paralysis and obstructive jaundice. (Khodaie and Sadeghpour, 2015). Among the large ginger family (Zingiberaceae) of about 1,300 species, ginger is grown for the hot, pungent flavor of the rhizome which can be used fresh, dried, ground or preserved (in brine, vinegar or sugar syrup) in most cases (WHDE, 2025). It grows annual stems of about a meter tall bearing narrow green leaves and yellow flowers, and in due time, the rhizome (ginger) is gathered when the stalk withers, immediately scalded, or washed and scraped, to kill it and prevent sprouting (NEPC, 2018). It is grown commercially in South and

Southeast Asia (India, China, Nepal), tropical Africa, parts of Central America and the Caribbean, and Australia where it takes about 8-10 months from planting to harvest the crop (WHDE, 2025). Fresh ginger contains moisture (80.9%), protein (2.3%), minerals (1.2%), fiber (2.4%), and carbohydrates (12.3%), with minerals like calcium, Iron, phosphorous, and vitamins such as thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, and vitamin C (Sharif *et al.*, 2018). Kaduna, Nasarawa, Benue, Niger, and Gombe States are the known producing states in Nigeria (NEPC, 2018). Some other states of Nigeria (with favorable soil) that produce little quantities, also contribute to the national and international ginger market. A typical example is Delta state (this study area region). Nigeria's main exporting countries are the Netherlands, United Kingdom, Germany and United Arab Emirates, while India, China, Bangladesh, Germany, Saudi Arabia, Netherlands, and United Arab Emirates are the importing countries (NEPC, 2018). A typical example of the ginger plant is presented in figure two (2) below, showing three descriptions. The (I) section presents a ginger cultivation, the (II) section shows a ginger plant with the purple coloured lines running through the leaves (almost ripening notice), and the (III) section shows the ginger plants with wilting leaves like burning leaves indicating the last stage of cultivation (already ripened and ready for harvest). These are presented in the figure below;

Figure 2: Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) cultivated in irrigation system with sprinkler placements (by site photography at study area)

II. MATERIALS

The main material used in the course of this research work was the research study area. The study area is the irrigation section in the demonstration station, at the soil and water engineering unit of the department of agricultural engineering, in Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Delta state of Nigeria, west africa. Other materials used include the ginger plants, sprinkler irrigation system, precipitation gauges, evaporimeter, logbook, site camera, *etc.*

III. METHODS

Relevant literatures were used in establishing tangible understanding relative to this research study. Upon scientific site measurements, precipitation readings of the study area were obtained prior installed and observed precipitation gauges. The values were used in obtaining the effective precipitation using numerical methods. The effective precipitation was further used in obtaining other valuable

results. In line with Brouwer, and Heibloem, (1986) of the food and agriculture organization (FAO) of the United Nations, irrigation required is a result of effectively used precipitation (P_e) subtraction from evapotranspiration (ET). This is mathematically presented as below;

$$IR = ET - P_e \quad \dots \text{(eq. 1)}$$

Where: IR is the irrigation water requirements. ET is the evaporation and transpiration, obtainable using pan measurements. P_e is precipitation effective, obtainable from precipitation (P), using two equations as below;

$$P_e = (0.8 P) - 25 \quad \dots \text{(eq. 2)}$$

$$P_e = (0.6 P) - 10 \quad \dots \text{(eq. 3)}$$

Note: The equation 2, is applicable when $P > 75$. Equation 3, is applicable when $P < 75$. And, either equation 2, or, equation 3, are usable when $P = 75$. However the choice of equation, when $P = 75$, the answer will be the same irrespective of the precipitation equation (above) used.

IV. RESULTS

The obtained results are presented in table one (1) below;

Table 1: Tabulated obtained results

S/N	Date (day)	Daily Precipitate Amount, P (mm)	Daily Effective Precipitation, Ep (mm)	Monthly Effective Precipitation, Ep (mm)	Evapotranspiration, ET (mm/day)	ET (mm/month)	Irrigation Water Requirements, IR (mm/day)	IR (mm/month)
1	1-31/01	0	0	0	8	248	8	248
2	1-29/02	0	0	0	8	232	8	232
3	25/03	252	177	2446	8	248	-169	-15
4	26/03	139	86		8		-78	
5	04/04	809	622		8		-614	
6	18/04	1455	1139		8		1131	
7	29/04	888	685	8	-677			
8	30/05	1,949	1534	3068	8	248	-1526	-2820
9	31/05	1,949	1534		8		-1526	
10	10/06	2,909	2302	6268	8	240	-2294	-6028
11	21/06	2,509	1982		7		-1975	

Okolotu G.I.

Advance Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology

Adv. J. Sci. Eng. Tech

Volume:11; Issue: 02

February -2026

ISSN: 2330 – 1744

Impact Factor: 9.16

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajset/index.php/ajset>

12	24/06	1,358	1061		8		-1053	
13	25/06	176	116		8		-108	
14	27/06	339	246		8		-238	
15	28/06	733	561		8		-553	
16	03/07	1,727	1357	9595	8	217	-1349	-9378
17	05/07	482	361		7		-354	
18	08/07	452	337		8		-329	
19	10/07	2,558	2021		7		-2014	
20	11/07	1,115	867		7		-860	
21	15/07	2,097	1653		8		-1645	
22	16/07	179	118		6		-112	
23	17/07	33	10		8		-2	
24	18/07	9	-5		6		11	
25	19/07	12	-3		8		11	
26	22/07	1,076	837		8		-829	
27	26/07	370	271		6		-265	
28	29/07	1,115	867		8		-859	
29	30/07	27	6		8		2	
30	02/08	376	276	2498	8	248	-268	-2250
31	12/08	194	130		8		-122	
32	13/08	270	191		8		-183	
33	15/08	21	3		8		5	
34	19/08	42	15		6		-9	
35	20/08	1,115	867		8		-859	
36	21/08	261	184		8		-176	
37	26/08	764	586		8		-578	
38	27/08	164	106		8		-98	
39	31/08	206	140		8		-132	
40	02/09	679	518	2497	8	240	-510	-2257
41	06/09	18	1		8		7	
42	09/09	648	493		8		-485	
43	10/09	497	373		8		-365	
44	11/09	876	676		8		-668	
45	19/09	115	67		8		-59	

Okolotu G.I.

46	23/09	330	239		8		-231	
47	27/09	194	130		8		-122	
48	02/10	1,324	1034	8835	7	248	-1027	-8587
49	04/10	21	3		8		5	
50	7/10	1,418	1109		8		-1101	
51	09/10	173	113		8		-105	
52	11/10	2,103	1657		8		-1649	
53	14/10	3,988	3165		8		-3157	
54	22/10	1,903	1497		8		-1489	
55	30/10	352	257		8		-249	
56	29/11	55	23		23		8	
57	1-31/12	0	0	0	8	248	8	248
Tota l	57	44,824	34595	35493	443	2897	-31890	- 3259 6
Av.	1	786	607	2958	8	241	-559	-2716

Cultivation interval of the ginger plants, in the research station, was March to December (excluding January and February values). During this period, effective precipitation recorded daily outcomes of 34595 mm on total with average of 629 mm, while the monthly total value was 35493 mm with average of 3549 mm. Evapotranspiration recorded a daily total of 427 mm with average of 8 mm, and monthly total of 2417 mm with average of 242 mm. And, irrigation water requirement obtained data yielded a total of -31906 mm with average of -580 mm on daily basis, and a total of -33076 mm with average of -3308 mm on monthly values.

V. DISCUSSION

In January and December, 248 mm of irrigation water was required to be available for plants optimum functions and yields. This was exactly equivalent to the crop water requirements. The crop water requirements, an ident of evapotranspiration, was significantly notable, even in the absence of precipitation, playing a vital role in the irrigation water requirements. This indice its role in water movement as well as picturing its impact in water management. Same precipitation absence was observed also in February except that the days of February months were less, thus yielding 232 mm. Since ginger plants cultivation is about nine (9) months on intermediate interval with respect to the specie type, irrigation provides avenue for water availability for its optimum cultivation

Okolotu G.I.

within the preferable months all - round the year in the study area and relative regions in line to its climate attributes. This is with respect to the annual six (6) months of dry season in Nigeria at large, which in most cases determine planting periods. While some farmers able to acquire irrigation system lack knowledge of the rate of application with respect to plants need.

Lack of comprehensive data hinders the development of effective design and strategies (Okolotu, 2024). These results adds to the existing data in facilitating various decision processes for irrigation experts, researchers, agriculturists, *etc.*, towards making effective conservation plan, designs, and, implementations. In line with Zaman, (2023) ideology, writing contributions on precision

References

CSU - CCCC, 2025. Understanding Plant Water Use: Evapotranspiration (ET). Colorado State University - Colorado Climate Center, CoAgMET. P 1. https://coagmet.colostate.edu/extended_etr_about.php

Okolotu G.I., Ikikiru D.F., Umunna M.F., & Eze C.S., 2025. Application Of The Hydroponic System For Soilless Cultivation Of Vegetable Plants In A Controlled Environment. Michigan Journal Of Engineering And Technology (MJET), Volume 13. Issue 3. P 2. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1706393_2

agriculture technologies will pave way for creating its awareness among the farmers and policymakers, as well as, serve as a guideline for its successful adoption. However these data were not previously available for the study area, thus it may also serve as a conservational data footprint.

VI. CONCLUSION

It was therefore concluded that the annual daily and monthly effective precipitation was 34595 mm and 35493 mm, with average of 607 mm and 2958 mm respectively. The evapotranspiration was 443 mm and 2897 mm, with average of 8 mm and 241 mm respectively. And, the irrigation water requirement was 31890 mm and 32596mm, with average of 559 mm and 2716 mm.

UCANR, 2025. ET: Evapotranspiration And Plant Water Use. University Of California Agriculture And Natural Resources (Center For Landscape & Urban Horticulture). P 3. <https://ucanr.edu/site/center-landscape-urban-horticulture/et-evapotranspiration-and-plant-water-use>

UCMP, 2025. Understanding Global Change - Precipitation. University Of California Museum Of Paleontology. P 1. <https://ugc.berkeley.edu/background-content/precipitation/>

WHDE, 2025. Ginger, Zingiber officinale. Wisconsin Horticulture Division Of Extension. University Of Wisconsin -

Okolotu G.I.

Advance Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology

Adv. J. Sci. Eng. Tech

Volume:11; Issue: 02

February -2026

ISSN: 2330 – 1744

Impact Factor: 9.16

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajset/index.php/ajset>

- Madison. P 1, & 3.
<https://hort.extension.wisc.edu/articles/ginger-zingiber-officinale/>
- CUSWL, 2024. Sustainable Water Resource Management - Evapotranspiration. Cornell University Sustainable Waters Lab - Department Of Natural Resources. P 1.
<https://blogs.cornell.edu/sustainablewaterresourcemanagement/evapotranspiration/>
- Okolotu G.I., 2024. Shear Stress Impact On Coastal Water Defense Structures In Asaba River Niger Waterways. Tuijin Jishu/ Journal Of Propulsion Technology. Volume 45. Number 3. P 3187.
www.propulsiontechjournal.com/index.php/journal/article/view/7718
- Okolotu G.I., Emumejaye E.P., Okareme F., Oluka S.I., Okeke C.G., Eje B.E., Eze P.C., & Ewhrudjakpor C.E., 2024. Investigation Of Textural Changes In Four Varieties Of Hybrid Tomato Cultivar Fruits Using The Warner Bratzler Shear Force Technique. Irish International Journal Of Engineering And Scientific Studies. Volume 7, Issue 4. P 20.
<https://aspjournals.org/journals/index.php/ijess/article/view/732/799>
- USACE - HEC, 2024. Precipitation Basic Concepts. HEC - HMS Technical Reference Manual. USACE Hydrologic Engineering Center. P 1.
<https://hec.usace.army.mil/confluence/hmsdocs/hmstrm/meteorology/precipitation/precipitation-basic-concepts>
- DETSIQ, 2023. Evaporation And Evapotranspiration. Department Of The Environment, Tourism, Science And Innovation, Queensland - WetlandInfo. P 1.
<https://wetlandinfo.des.qld.gov.au/wetlands/ecology/processes-systems/evaporation/>
- Muratoglu A., Bilgen G.K., Angin I., & Kodal S., 2023. Performance Analyses Of Effective Rainfall Estimation Methods For Accurate Quantification Of Agricultural Water Footprint. Water Research. Volume 238. Number 120011. P 11.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120011>
- NGS, 2023. Precipitation. National Geographic Society. P 1.
<https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/precipitation/>
- NOAA, 2023. The Hydrologic Cycle. National Oceanic And Atmospheric Administration. P 1.
<https://noaa.gov/jetstream/atmosphere/hydro>

Okolotu G.I.

Advance Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology

Adv. J. Sci. Eng. Tech

Volume:11; Issue: 02

February -2026

ISSN: 2330 – 1744

Impact Factor: 9.16

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajset/index.php/ajset>

Sundberg M.D., 2023. Evapotranspiration (ET).

Ebsco. P 1. <https://ebSCO.com/research-starters/environmental-sciences/evapotranspiration-et>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-819527-7.00001-7>

Zaman Q.U., 2023. Precision Agriculture Evolution, Insights And Emerging Trends. Chapter 1 - Precision Agriculture Technology: A Pathway Toward Sustainable Agriculture. Science Direct. P 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-443-18953-1.00013-1>

Fitton N., Alexander P., Arnell N., Bajzelj B., Calvin K., Doelman J., Gerber J.S., Havlik P., Hasegawa T., Herrero M., Krisztin T., Van Meijl H., Powell T., Sands R., Stehfest E., West P.C., & Smith P., 2019. The Vulnerabilities Of Agricultural Land And Food Production To Future Water Scarcity. Global Environmental Change. Volume 58, Number 101944. P 2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2019.101944>

Wanniarachchi S., & Sarukkalige R., 2022. A Review On Evapotranspiration Estimation In Agricultural Water Management: Past, Present, And Future. Hydrology. Volume 9. Issue 7. P 11 & 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/hydrology9070123>

Vasconcelos M.S., Mota E.F., Gomes-Rochette N.F., Nunes-Pinheiro D.C.S., Nabavi S.M., & Melo D.F., 2019. Ginger (Zingiber Officinale Roscoe). Chapter 3.18. Nonvitamin And Nonmineral Nutritional Supplements. Volume 2019. P 237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812491-8.00034-5>

Liang S., & Wang J., 2020. Advanced Remote Sensing (Second Edition). Chapter 16 - Precipitation. Terrestrial Information Extraction And Applications. Volume 2020, P 621. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-815826-5.00016-7>

WSC - USGS, 2019a. Evaporation And The Water Cycle. Water Science School - US Geological Survey. P 1 & 6. <https://usgs.gov/water-science-school/science/evaporation-and-water-cycle#overview>

Mylonas I., Stavrakoudis D., Katsantonis D., & Korpetis E., 2020. Climate Change And Food Security With Emphasis On Wheat. Chapter 1 - Better Farming Practices To Combat Climate Change. Science Direct. Volume 2020. P 27.

WSC - USGS, 2019b. Precipitation And The Water Cycle. Water Science School - US Geological Survey. P 1.

Okolotu G.I.

<https://usgs.gov/water-science-school/science/precipitation-and-water-cycle#overview>

NEPC, 2018. Ginger – Profile. Nigerian Export Promotion Council. Government Of Nigeria. P 2, & 4.
<https://nepc.gov.ng/blog/market-report/ginger-profile/>

Sharif M.K., Ejaz R., & Pasha I., 2018. Nutritional And Therapeutic Potential Of Spices. Chapter 11. Therapeutic, Probiotic, And Unconventional Foods. Volume 2018, P 187.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814625-5.00011-X>

Jakribettu R.P., Bolor R., Bhat H.P., Thaliath A., Haniadka R., Rai M.P., George T., & Baliga M.S., 2016. Ginger (Zingiber Officinale Rosc.) Oils. Chapter 50. Essential Oils In Food Preservation, Flavor And Safety. Volume 2016. P 451.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-416641-7.00050-X>

Khodaie L., & Sadeghpour O., 2015. Ginger From Ancient Times To The New Outlook. Jundishapur Journal Of Natural Pharmaceutical Products. Volume 10. Issue 1. P 2.
<https://doi.org/10.17795/jjnpp-18402>

Brouwer C., & Heibloem M., 1986. Principles Of Irrigation Water Needs - Chapter 4: Irrigation Water Needs. Irrigation Water Management - Training Manual Of The Food And Agriculture Organization, Rome. Volume 3. Part Number 1. P 1.
<https://fao.org/4/s2022e/s2022e04.htm#TopOfPage>
<https://fao.org/4/s2022e/s2022e00.htm#Contents>